

Intraluminal sensor-actor-system for tactile vessel diagnosis and model based individualized vessel reconstruction

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Abstract: This short report emphasized on results acquired by 3 research groups of Furtwangen University cooperating in the project associated with the field of personalized medicine and digitalization within the operating room. The main research question to answer was: Is an intraluminal reconstruction of the urethra via a miniaturized sensor-actor system and a model-based vessel reconstruction possible? The design and fabrication of a flexible sensor-actor system and Finite Element simulation results are presented. For the final goal of vessel reconstruction, tissue repair characteristics were investigated.

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I. Introduction

Injuries and strictures of the urogenital tract are relative common complications after radiation treatment and operations within the abdominal and pelvis region. Exemplary, scarring after radiation treatment of patients with Cervix carcinoma was noted in 1,8 % to 2,7 % during a 10-year follow-up. Further, tissue traumas are often resulting from catheterization or prostatectomies in males. Without treatment such damage may lead to severe short- or long-term complications [1–3].

In this project a new endoscopic method for the intraluminal reconstruction of urethral strictures and injuries was investigated. Via an embedded flexible sensor-actor-system which can be inserted as balloon catheter with a common cystoscope, tissue parameters such as elasticity and tensile strength can be evaluated, while correlating models allow a data interpretation for an optimal therapy, e.g., to choose a suitable reconstruction method. Results of the sensor-actor development, the biological experiments looking for suitable reconstruction methods and the modelling of the tissue and the sensor-tissue interaction are presented.

II. Materials and Methods

II.1. Sensor-Actor Development

The sensor element is based on an elastomer balloon platform, aiming for a tactile probing of the vessel lumen biomechanics by inflation and comparison with reference datasets. The sensors are monolithically integrated in the balloon-elastomer wall utilizing the morphological variance of ultrathin 40 nm thick gold (Au) films. For the sensor part an upscaled demonstrator was realized while the inherent actor capabilities of the balloon due to a tactile contact with the surrounding tissue were also

conceptionally evaluated. Demonstrators were manufactured by adapting conventionally micro system manufacturing processes to the elastomeric platform. According planar metal structures were created by lift-off processes and thin film deposition using shadow masks which allow patterning without etching on wafer level (**Figure 1**). The transfer to elastomeric base balloons allowed the integration of metal films into the balloon wall.

Figure 1 Schematic of the main manufacturing steps for the functionalized elastomer-membranes, later integrated via a transfer membrane process on the base balloon [4].

Via O₂-plasma pre-treatment the needed morphology of the films can be adjusted. The imposed strain due to balloon inflation is thereby compensated within the self-similar architectures of the conductor lines with a closed wavy morphology (\approx const. resistance), while propagating micro- and nano-cracks in the straight sensor segments lead to a resistance increase due to the circumferential expansion, directly correlated with the strain level. In **Figure 2** an inflated upscaled demonstrator is shown in combination with the varying surface morphologies at different sites of the embedded ultrathin metal film.

II.II. Modelling

As the technological system development, modelling was also focused on the sensing and thus the interaction of high compliant elastomer balloons with surrounding tissue segments. 2D and 3D state of the art Finite-Element (FE) models were utilized for forward modelling, while in depth analysis of the interaction sequences lead to inverse formulations for the interpretation of idealized strain data, provided by the balloon sensor in the targeted application scenario (e.g. [5]). In **Figure 3** a FE-Model for in-depth analysis of interaction sequences between a high compliant balloon with non-cylindrical vessel segments is shown [6].

Figure 2 Upscaled and inflated demonstrator at the bottom of the image and exemplary scanning electron images of the surface morphology in sensing and conductor line regions.

Figure 3 FE-model of a high compliant balloon segment and a fiber based non-cylindrical two-layer tissue segment in the reference configuration [6].

II.III. Biological Experiments

The biological experiments focused on the reconstruction of teared urethral tissue segments. As for an intraluminal minimally-invasive approach reconstruction via gluing would be advantage compared to conventional suturing techniques, these two methods were compared. After establishing suitable sequences enabling up to 21-day cultivation of porcine tissue samples, trypan blue staining and histological cryostat section analysis via Hemalaun-Eosin and van Gieson staining was utilized, to evaluate the repair characteristics after gluing and suturing in longitudinal and axial cuts.

Figure 4 Exemplary van Gieson staining of sutured end-to-end anastomosis of porcine urethras for 4 days, showing well regrowth characteristics of the tissue area at the suture point.

III. Results and discussion

Process and manufacturing techniques for monolithically integrated ultrathin Au-films in elastomer-balloon walls were successfully applied to manufacture 5:1 upscaled demonstrators. The integrity of the varying surface morphology was checked at the intermediate process steps and the membrane transfer allowed the embedding of Au films without deteriorating the fragile morphology.[4] State-of-the art FE-models of the tissue and the balloon material were combined to simulate the balloon-tissue interaction, and first design guidelines for the sensor-balloon as well as methods for the inverse identification of biomechanical tissue properties from sensor readings were derived (e.g. [5, 6]). The biological experiments revealed, that conventional suturing techniques were superior compared to gluing reconstruction, which complicates the intraluminal reconstruction and a suitable miniaturized system must account for possible intraluminal suturing in a confined space.

IV. Conclusions

Within the course of this project, multiple aspects for a miniaturized intraluminal sensor-actor-system for tactile vessel diagnostic and model based individual vessel reconstruction were evaluated and presented to the research community. Aside the selected prior mentioned main results, infrastructure and competences in the field of flexible sensors and modelling of tissue could be established at the involved institutes and lead to a recently started new project aiming for a diagnostic balloon-catheter for tactile blood vessel diagnosis.

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